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ANALYSIS OF RECENT STUDIES ON THE PROCESSING OF MINERAL RAW MATERIALS IN THE LOWER AMU DARYA REGION

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the recent scientific research conducted in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the processing of mineral raw materials in the Lower Amu Darya region. The studies mainly focus on the production of magnesium-phosphorus fertilizers and the use of phosphorites to neutralize acidic wastewater from the oil and fat industry, resulting in the production of magnesium-phosphorus and organomineral fertilizers. It also covers the production of complex fertilizers through acid treatment of local phosphate raw materials, the composition of talc-magnesite from the Zinelbuloq deposit, the properties of quartz sands from the Khiva deposit, and a review of the latest research on feldspar, sandstone, and porphyry raw materials in the Lower Amu Darya region.

Keywords: *phosphorites, talc-magnesite, quartz sand, feldspars, waste neutralization, complex and liquid fertilizers, organomineral fertilizers, cement.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Havola qilinayotgan Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasining Quyi Amudaryo hududidagi mineral xomashyolarni qayta ishlash bo'yicha so'nggi yillarda olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlar tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotlar asosan magniy-fosforli o'g'itlar olishda hamda yog' moy sanoati kislotali chqindi suvlarini fosforitlar yordamida neytrallash orqali magniy-fosforli hamda organomineral o'g'itlar ishlab chiqarishda qo'llanilishi, mahalliy fosfatli xomashyolarni kislotali ishlov berish orqali murakkab o'g'itlar olinishi, Zinelbuloq konining talk-magnazit tarkibi, Xiva konining kvarts qumlari xossalari, shuningdek, Quyi Amudaryo xududidagi kvarsli xomashyolar dala shpati, peschanik va porfirit xomashyolarini o'rganish bo'yicha nashr qilingan so'nggi ilmiy tadqiqotlar taxlili yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *fosforitlar, talk-magnazit, kvarts qumi, dala shpatlari, chiqindilarni neytrallash, kompleks va suyuq o'g'itlar, organomineral o'g'itlar, sement.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируются научные исследования, проведённые в последние годы в Республике Узбекистан по переработке минерального сырья в Нижнеамударинском регионе. Основное внимание уделено применению этих исследований в получении магний-фосфорных удобрений, а также в производстве магний-фосфорных и органоминеральных удобрений путём нейтрализации кислотных сточных вод масложировой промышленности с использованием фосфоритов. Освещены вопросы получения сложных удобрений путём кислотной обработки местного фосфатного сырья, изучения состава тальк-магнезитового сырья месторождения Зинельбулак, свойств кварцевых песков месторождения Хива, а также анализа последних научных работ по изучению кварцсодержащего сырья полевого шпат, песчаник и порфирит Нижнеамударинского региона.

Ключевые слова: *фосфориты, тальк-магнезит, кварцевый песок, полевые шпаты, нейтрализация отходов, комплексные и жидкие удобрения, органоминеральные удобрения, цемент.*

INTRODUCTION

The Lower Amu Darya region is one of the key economic zones of the Republic of Uzbekistan with significant potential in mineral resources. A thorough physicochemical investigation of the composition and properties of the region's georesources enables the transformation of these natural materials into high value-added products.

In recent years, scientific research has increasingly focused on the in-depth study of these mineral raw materials and on developing environmentally sustainable and economically efficient technologies for their processing.

This article summarizes the most recent scientific studies related to the processing of mineral raw materials located in the Lower Amu Darya region. The analysis focuses on their potential applications in industrial sectors, their ecological and economic advantages, and presents scientific conclusions that can form the basis for the development of promising technologies.

The Republic of Karakalpakstan and the Khorezm region, located in the Lower Amu Darya region, are rich in mineral raw material resources and represent a focus of advanced research on their processing. It is known that the Sultan Uvays mountain range contains talc ore deposits, with reserves in categories B+C₁ amounting to 68 million tons and in category C₂ totaling 15.7 million tons. Overall, the deposits contain approximately 83.7 million tons of talc and talc-magnesite [1–3]. Furthermore, the southern part of this mountain range—including the districts of Qorauzak, Beruniy,

and Amudarya—is home to the Sultan Uvays deposit of feldspars with reserves of 2.6 million tons [4], sedimentary sandstone located 55 km southeast of Nukus in Qorauzak district, and a porphyry deposit with estimated reserves of 63 million tons located 80 km southeast of the Kegeyli settlement in Qorauzak district [5–6], which are considered among the main mineral raw materials of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

In the Khorezm region, which is also part of the Lower Amu Darya area, quartz-based raw materials are prevalent. These include quartz sand deposits with feldspar content, such as those found in the Khiva and Yangiarik regions. The total reserves of these deposits are estimated at over 2 million tons [4, 7–8].

These studies are aimed at exploring the potential for efficient utilization of locally available raw materials in industrial and agricultural applications. The current scientific work analyzes the main research directions focused on beneficiation of mineral raw materials and their use, as well as the expansion of the industrial raw material base.

One of the pressing global issues today is ensuring a growing population with access to quality food, construction materials, and essential goods. An effective approach to solving this issue is the development of innovative technologies grounded in modern science, which can enable the processing of local raw materials to produce high-quality, export-oriented products that substitute imports and meet current market demands.

One of the most efficient ways to stabilize food supply is by increasing crop yields and preventing the degradation of agricultural lands. It is well known that, in addition to the primary nutrients nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, the presence of macronutrients such as magnesium, sulfur, and calcium is critically important for healthy plant growth and high productivity [9].

In this regard, a number of scientific studies have been carried out by researchers in our Republic on the production of various phosphorus-containing fertilizers from Central Kyzylykum phosphorites [9–13]. In the scientific works published by the authors of this article, processes have been studied for producing azosuperphosphates with a composition of (wt.%) N – 2.5% and P₂O₅ – 14%, as well as magnesium-containing azosuperphosphates with optimal N-P-Mg-Ca-S ratios and a composition of (wt.%) P₂O₅ – 9.02, MgO_{s.e} – 8.13, CaO – 29.60, SO₃ – 30.80, and N – 2.2, from low-grade Central Kyzylykum phosphorites. The studies also present the theoretical basis for the effective use of a 40% aqueous solution of ammonium sulfate ((NH₄)₂SO₄) in sulfuric acid, with the aim of enhancing the granulation efficiency and improving the mechanical properties of the fertilizer granules.

In addition, in this context, researchers have determined that using low-grade phosphorites with a total P₂O₅ content of 9.11% in a 100:20 ratio at 60 °C is optimal

for neutralizing acidic wastewater generated in the oil and fat industry. The activated phosphorites were composted with cattle manure at a 100:10 ratio for 90 days, and as a result, organomineral fertilizers with a plant-available P_2O_5 content of 52.11% were obtained [14; 15]. The agrochemical test results of the resulting organomineral fertilizers demonstrated a positive effect [16–18]. The chemical composition of the acidic wastewater produced in the oil and fat industry was also thoroughly analyzed by these researchers [19–21].

Furthermore, in the studies [9, 22–25], the authors used magnesite-containing waste derived from the talc-bearing rocks of the Zinelbulak region in the Sulton Uvays mountain range for the production of complex magnesium-containing azosuperphosphates comprising N-P-Mg-Ca-S elements. The composition (in wt.%) of the waste material included 53.70% magnesite, 27.20% talc, 9.09% calcite, and dolomite.

The mineralogical and physicochemical composition of talc-magnesite rocks from the Zinelbulak deposit has been thoroughly investigated [1, 22, 25–27]. In the studies conducted by the authors, XRD, XRF, and IR-spectral analyses of selected samples revealed an average content of talc ($Mg_3Si_4O_{10}(OH)_2$) ranging from 60–61%, and magnesite ($MgCO_3$) ranging from 27–28%. The analyses also identified the presence of 5–12% chlorite, 3–12% magnetically active materials, and approximately 1–5% calcite and dolomite.

Thermal analysis using TG-DTA showed that between 16–419 °C, a 1.64% mass loss corresponds to the release of physically bound water from talc. Between 419–752 °C, a 9.95% mass loss was attributed to the decomposition of magnesite, calcite, and dolomite, with the evolution of CO_2 gas. At 917 °C, an additional 3.88% mass loss was observed, associated with the oxidation of talc crystals, resulting in the formation of $MgSiO_3$ and SiO_2 .

Grinding experiments on the talc-magnesite sample indicated that the material has a hardness of 1 on the Mohs scale, and over 90% of the crushed particles were found to be smaller than 15–20 μm in size. Such structural characteristics indicate the industrial applicability of talc-magnesite raw materials, particularly for the production of magnesia-based binders, amorphous silica, and fertilizers. Consequently, these findings highlight the potential for expanding the raw material base for industries engaged in the production of these valuable products.

Today, innovative approaches aimed at reducing the carbon footprint and ensuring environmental sustainability are gaining increasing importance in the cement industry. In the studies by authors cited in references [5–6], the creation of modern composite Portland cements, the diversity of their constituents, and the functional properties of those constituents have been analysed in depth.

These findings are closely connected with the experimental work conducted by the young researcher A. Sh. Khadjiev of Urgench State University and co-authors [28], who investigated how the sandstone component alters the physicochemical interactions within the cement composition. Khadjiev's research demonstrates that the participation of silicate rocks is crucial in forming the crystal structure of cement and the binder phases that confer strength. In related works [29–30], the same author examined how these processes can lower the carbon footprint of cement manufacture, showing scientifically that the chemical reactivity of silicate rocks, when incorporated into cement, can markedly reduce CO₂ emissions.

The authors' results indicate that stabilising cement production technology and increasing energy efficiency can make a significant contribution to mitigating today's adverse climate impacts. Industrially, these developments offer both the valorisation of waste into high-value products and conservation of natural raw-material resources. Samples taken from the feldspar deposit of the Sultan Uvays area in the Lower Amu Darya region were studied by SEM-EDS and found to contain, by mass, Si = 31.98 %, K = 8.32 %, Al = 8.89 %, and Na = 2.16 %. XRD and IR analyses established that the mineralogical composition comprises 60–65 % microcline (K-feldspar), 21–25 % albite (Na-feldspar), 7–10 % α -quartz, and 2–3 % calcite. This composition confirms the suitability of the feldspar raw material for the production of high-quality glass and ceramics [4].

Continuing in this direction, the authors analysed quartz sands from the "Khiva" deposit in Khorezm province. Their studies [7] determined key parameters of these sands, such as particle-size distribution, SiO₂ content, and iron-oxide level. In reference [8], they proposed a beneficiation technology for these sands. The authors thus scientifically substantiated the possibility of obtaining a high-quality quartz concentrate suitable for glass and ceramic production. The conclusions emphasize that the purity of quartz sands and the concentration of SiO₂ are critical factors in glass manufacturing.

CONCLUSION

Based on an analysis of recent research on the processing of mineral raw materials in the Lower Amu Darya region, it can be concluded that the region's geo-resources - specifically phosphorites, talc-magnesite rocks, quartz sands, and feldspars - possess significant economic and industrial potential.

The composition of talc-magnesite ores from the Zinelbulak deposit offers considerable opportunities not only for fertilizer production but also for the manufacture of amorphous silica and magnesian binders. The high content of talc and magnesite justifies the economic feasibility of obtaining valuable products through comprehensive processing of these ores. Meanwhile, the physicochemical

characterization of the quartz-feldspar sands from the Khiva deposit and feldspars from the Sultan Uvays deposit supports their use as primary raw materials in glass, ceramics, and glass enamel industries.

It is also worth emphasizing that all the studies under review are complementary in nature, providing a basis for developing sustainable industrial technologies based on the mineral raw materials of the Lower Amu Darya region. In this context, scientifically grounded, environmentally safe, and economically efficient approaches hold particular importance.

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